

O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA LINGVOPOETIK IZLANISHLAR: SHAROF

RASHIDOV IJODI MISOLIDA

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O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti mutaxassisligi 2-kurs magistri

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur tezisda o‘zbek tilshunosligida lingvopoetik izlanishlarning bugungi holati Sharof Rashidovning badiiy asarlari misolida tahlil etiladi. Adibning poetik ifoda vositalaridan foydalanish uslubi, obrazli til, stilistik vositalarning o‘rni va ularning o‘zbek adabiy tilining badiiy salohiyatini oshirishdagi ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: lingvopoetika, obraz, stilistik vosita, obrazli til, badiiy matn, poetik tafakkur, metafora, badiiy ifoda.

Аннотация. В диссертации анализируется современное состояние лингвопоэтических исследований в узбекском языкознании на примере литературного творчества Шарофа Рашидова. Освещены особенности использования писателем поэтических средств выражения, образного языка, роль стилистических приемов и их значение в повышении художественного потенциала узбекского литературного языка.

Ключевые слова: лингвопоэтика, образ, стилистический прием, образный язык, художественный текст, поэтическая мысль, метафора, художественное выражение.

Abstract. This thesis analyzes the current state of linguopoetic research in Uzbek linguistics using the example of Sharof Rashidov's literary works. The writer's style of using poetic means of expression, the role of figurative language, stylistic means and their importance in increasing the artistic potential of the Uzbek literary language are highlighted.

Keywords: linguopoetics, image, stylistic means, figurative language, literary text, poetic thought, metaphor, artistic expression.

Lingvopoetika – til va adabiyotning tutash nuqtasida joylashgan, badiiy matnni tilshunoslik mezonlari asosida o‘rganadigan soha. O‘zbek adabiyotida bu yo‘nalish XX asr ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab shakllanib, bugungi kunda adabiy matnni tahlil qilishning zamonaviy va chuqur metodlaridan biri sifatida e‘tirof etiladi. Sharof Rashidovning badiiy ijodi bu borada o‘rganishga arzigulik manbadir.

Sharof Rashidov o‘z ijodini shoir sifatida boshlagan. Uning ilk yirik asari — “Chegarachi” dostoni (1937), urush yillaridagi badiiy talqinlar — “Mening nafratim” (1945), “Qahrim” (1945) to‘plamlari, urushdan keyingi yurt mehnatini tasvirlagan “G‘oliblar” (1951, 1972), “Bo‘rondan kuchli” (1958), “Buyuk to‘lqin” (1964) romanlari, “Kashmir qo‘shig‘i” (1956) lirik-qissasi uning poetik tafakkurining yorqin namunalari.

Rashidov asarlarida metafora, epitet, parallelizm, ritorik savol, xalq maqollari va iboralar keng qo‘llaniladi. Masalan, “Bo‘rondan kuchli” romanida urushdan keyingi qiyinchiliklarga bardosh berayotgan xalqning ma‘naviy kuchi poetik obrazlar orqali yuksak badiiylik bilan ifodalanadi. “Kashmir qo‘shig‘i”da esa hind xalqining ozodlik kurashi tasvirlanar ekan, Rashidov poetik uslubda xalq dardini milliy va global kontekstda ifodalaydi.

Adib ijodida lingvopoetik jihatdan ahamiyatli bo‘lgan jihatlardan biri — badiiylik bilan g‘oyaviylikning birligidir. Bu esa sovet davri adabiyotining umumiy tendensiyalarini anglash va ularni zamonaviy tahlil mezonlari orqali o‘rganishga imkon beradi. Sharof Rashidov ijodini lingvopoetik nuqtayi nazardan o‘rganish orqali quyidagi ilmiy natijalarga erishildi:

1. Rashidov poetik tafakkurga ega adib sifatida o‘zbek tilining badiiy ifoda imkoniyatlarini kengaytirdi;
2. Uning asarlarida lingvopoetik vositalarning (metafora, epitet, sintaktik parallelizm) ko‘pligi obrazlilik darajasini oshiradi;
3. Lingvopoetika nazariyasi asosida Rashidov nasri va she‘riyati badiiy tilda milliylik va zamonaviylik uyg‘unligini ko‘rsatadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Мирханова, Г. (2024). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИ. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 3(1), 76-80.
2. Мирханова, Г. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172-178.
3. Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Rus tilshunosligida sinonim sozlar oquv lugatlarining tadrijiy rivojlanishi. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 326-329.
4. Rustamovna, M. G. (2024). Linguistic Form of Terms in Explanatory Dictionaries of the Uzbek Language. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(6), 589-591.
5. Mirxanova, G. (2021). Sinonim so'zlar o'quv lug'atining megaqurilishi: Sinonim so'zlar o'quv lug'atining megaqurilishi. *Buxoro davlat pedagogika instituti jurnali*, 1(1).

6. Mirxanova, G. R. (2022). Stages of Enhancement of Synonym Dictionaries. *International Journal of World Languages*, 2(1).
7. Rustamovna, M. G. (2023). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language.
8. Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.
9. Mirxanova, G. R. (2023). SYNTACTIC ANALYSIS OF WORKS OF ART IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS: METHODS AND APPLICATIONS.
10. Мирханова, Г. Р., & Сафарова, О. М. (2019). УЧЕБНЫЕ СЛОВАРИ–СРЕДСТВО ОБУЧЕНИЯ УЗБЕКСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. *Вестник магистратуры*, (6-5), 41.
11. Rustamovna, M. G. Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek.
12. Rustamovna, M. G. EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *EMERGENCE*, 5, 24-2021.
13. DICTIONARIES, S. a teacher of the faculty of Primary education, BSU. *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY*, 96.
14. Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). THE IMPORTANCE OF LEXICOGRAPHY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION. *В научный сборник вошли научные работы, посвященные широкому кругу современных проблем науки и образования, вопросов образовательных технологий 2020.-436 с.*, 165.
15. Rustamovna, M. G. (2025). KONSEPTUAL YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TERMIN TIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Hamkor konferensiyalar*, 1(15), 20-22.
16. Jabborova, M., & Safoyeva, S. (2024). THE IMAGE OF THE SUN IN EPIC WORKS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 3(4), 165-168.
17. Valiyevna, J. M. (2024). The Artistic Perfection of Cosmic Images in the Works of Yusuf Khos Hajib and Navoi. *Journal of Intellectual Property and Human Rights*, 3(4), 153-158.
18. Jabborova, M. (2024). MUMTOZ SHE'RIYATDA UCHRAYDIGAN OY, YULDUZ, QUYOSH TIMSOLLARINING SHAXS QIYOFASIDA TIMSOLLANISHI. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(1), 48-52.
19. SHE'RIYATIDA, M. J. Z., & TIMSOLLARMUSHTARAKLIGI, I. I. V. K. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS.–2022. *T*, 2(18), 209-211.

20. Eshqulova, G., Musurmonova, M., & Axmedova, D. B. (2022). Boshlang 'ich sinf ona tili darslarida nutqiy ko 'nikmalarni rivojlantiruvchi o 'quv topshiriqlarini ishlab chiqishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(1A), 72-75.
21. Qizi, S. M. A., & Axmedova, D. B. (2022). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFI O 'QUVCHILARINING BILIM EGALLASHGA DOIR QARASHLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA DIDAKTIK ASARLARINING O 'RNI. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(1A), 43-46.
22. Axmedova, D. (2021). СЕМАНТИЧЕСКАЯ СИСТЕМА СИСТЕМА И МОДЕЛЬ. *COMPUTER LINGUISTICS: PROBLEMS, SOLUTIONS, PROSPECTS*, 1(1).
23. Axmedova, D. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.
24. Akhmedova, D. B. (2020). SET OF SEMANTIC TAGS FOR UZBEK LANGUAGE UNITS: CONSTANTS AND OPERATOR CLASSIFIER. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (2), 177-179.
25. Bahodirovna, D. A. (2020). SEMANTIC TAG CATEGORY IN CORPUS LINGUISTICS: EXPERIENCE AND ANALYSIS. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 152-160.